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URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D2.6 – Ecosystem services and tourism in the URBAN WASTE pilot cities

Final version

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Authors:	Christian Fertner, Juliane Große University of Copenhagen		

Abstract

This report (Deliverable 2.6) deals with the connection of ecosystem services and tourism. Understanding how ecosystem services contribute to touristic experiences fosters engaging in practices related to sustainable tourism. This plays an important role for waste production and management in the 11 pilot cities of the EU H2020 URBAN WASTE project.

A first version of this report reviewed relevant literature and summarized results from a survey on tourists' and tourist staff's perceptions of ecosystems services in the cities, conducted in URBAN WASTE's work package 3. In this version, we added a description of selected ecosystem services in the cities, which were identified in consultation with city partners. The final section provides a benchmark of the cities' state of environment based on various European and global datasets, resulting in city profiles. The results of this report can be used in the later work on strategies (work package 4) and impact assessment (work package 7).

Contributors

NAME	COMPANY	CONTRIBUTIONS INCLUDE
Christian Fertner, Juliane Große	UCPH	Elaboration of report

List of abbreviations

UCPH	University of Copenhagen
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
CoP	Communities of Practices
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
EU	The European Union
EC	European Commission
EASME	European Agency for Small and Medium Enterprises
ES	Ecosystem Services

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Understanding how ecosystem services contribute to touristic experiences fosters engaging in practices related to sustainable tourism.

1 Introduction

This report deals with the connection of ecosystem services and tourism. Understanding how ecosystem services contribute to touristic experiences fosters engaging in practices related to sustainable tourism, which plays an important role for waste production and management in the 11 pilot cities of the URBAN WASTE project.

The report provides an overview of the relation between ecosystem services and tourism, based on a short literature review (**Chapter 2**) and results from a survey with tourists and tourist workers in the pilot cities (**Chapter 4**). There is no consensus in the literature on how to assess ecosystem services and empirical research on cultural and urban ecosystem services is limited. Most relevant in the context of URBAN WASTE are some provisioning services and a variety cultural services, incl. recreation, ecotourism, aesthetics, and services of spiritual, learning and heritage importance. The survey shows that freshwater provision, local food provision and cultural heritage are evaluated very important in all cities.

Figure 1: Categories of provisioning / cultural ecosystem services used in this report

Based on the survey and consultation with city partners we selected examples of ecosystem services in the pilot cities and describe their characteristics in eleven fact sheets (**Chapter 5**). The fact sheets illustrate the great variety of ecosystem services relevant for tourism. In **Chapter 6** we return to the city scale to conduct a benchmark of the cities' state of the spatial environment based on various European and global datasets. Results from this work can be used in the later work on strategies (WP4 – e.g. How can selected ecosystem services be used to improve tourism and waste management, or which impacts on selected ecosystem services should be considered when developing strategies) and impact assessment (WP7).

2 Reviewing ecosystem services and their relation to tourism

2.1 The concept of Ecosystem Services (ES)

“Ecosystems are shaped by the interaction of communities of living organisms with the abiotic environment. [...] Ecosystem functions are defined as the capacity or the potential to deliver ecosystem services. Ecosystem services are, in turn, derived from ecosystem functions and represent the realized flow of services for which there is demand.” (Maes et al., 2013, p. 16)

In this sense, ecosystems provide benefits – goods and services – for people. Ecosystem services are conceptualised (see Figure 2) by linking “socio-economic systems with ecosystems via the flow of ecosystem services” (Maes et al., 2013, p. 16).

Figure 2: Conceptual framework for EU wide ecosystem assessments (Maes et al., 2013)

2.2 Typologies of ecosystem services

Within the concept of ecosystem services, exist different approaches and typologies of ecosystem services. Currently three main international classification systems are available.

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005) is one of the main sources for the definition of ecosystem services and its connection to human well-being. Ecosystem services are organised in four groups:

- Provisioning services (Food, fresh water, wood and fibre, fuel, ...)
- Regulating services (Climate regulation, flood regulation, disease regulation, water purification, ...)
- Cultural services (Aesthetic, spiritual, educational , recreational, ...)
- Supporting services (Nutrient cycling, soil formation, primary production, ...)

This classification was further developed by TEEB and CICES. “The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity” approach (TEEB, 2010) links economics to ecosystem services and ecology. The TEEB classification of ecosystem services considers:

- Provisioning services (food, water, raw materials, gens, medicinal resources, ornamental resources)
- Regulating services (air, climate, extreme events, water flows, water treatment, erosion, soil, pollination, biological)
- Habitat or supporting services (maintenance of life cycles and genetic diversity)
- Cultural and amenity services (aesthetics, recreation and tourism, inspiration, spiritual, cognitive development)

“The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Service” (CICES) (EEA, 2017a) has only three main classes of ecosystem services:

- Provisioning services
- Regulation and Maintenance services
- Cultural services.

We will base our further work on ecosystem services in the URBAN WASTE project on CICES, as it is the most current classification and used by important agencies as the European Environment Agency.

2.3 Mapping and assessment of ecosystem services

A major challenge – and consequently a diversity of approaches – lies in mapping and assessing ecosystem services at specific sites or areas. The development and improvement of indicators is a major topic in much of contemporary research on ecosystem service mapping and assessment.

Urban areas, cities and towns are “*both consumers and producers of ecosystem services*” (Sandhu & Wratten, 2013, p. 11), as they depend very much on the surrounding ecosystems to fulfil daily needs. However, urban green spaces also provide ecosystem services themselves. Haase et al. (2014, p. 414) promote the importance of urban ecosystems by emphasizing that “functioning ecosystems provide the flexibility in urban landscapes to build adaptive capacity and cope with problems such as increased risks of heat waves and flooding”. Considering the challenges of rapid urbanisation and sustainable development the benefits of urban biodiversity on well-being in cities gains even more importance. Haase et al. (2014, p. 414) name a “*diverse set of land uses, including parks, cemeteries, golf courses, watercourses, avenues, gardens and yards, verges, commons, green roofs and facades, sports fields, vacant lots, industrial sites, and landfills*” that provide urban ecosystem services.

Haase et al. (2014) conducted a meta-analysis on scientific papers published on urban ecosystem services. As part of their results, they show that only 0.2% of the studies (217 in total) dealt with tourism. In contrast, an empirical review on cultural ecosystem services (Hernández-Morcillo, Plieninger, & Bieling, 2013) finds that more than 50% of the used indicators (42 studies in total) address recreation and (eco)tourism. However, overall, cultural ecosystem services are yet rarely taken into consideration in ecosystem service research (Schaich, Bieling, & Plieninger, 2010). Daniel et al. (2012, p. 8813) also state that the “*importance of cultural services has consistently been recognized, but in the rare instances in which there is any further consideration, they are often characterized as being “intangible,” “subjective,” and difficult to quantify in biophysical or monetary terms [...], thus retarding their integration into the ES framework.*”

Combining those findings, there appears to exist a gap in addressing tourism related ecosystem services, particularly in urban areas. Likewise is the development of indicators for the assessment of urban ecosystems still challenging; redundancy in indicators, linking indicators to benefits and services as well as capacity of indicators to capture services at multiple spatial and temporal scales are only some of the challenges (Haase et al., 2014).

A comprehensive approach towards capturing urban ES was conducted as part of the MAES project – Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (Maes et al., 2016). Urban ecosystems are in their understanding recognised as socio-ecological systems that are composed by the following elements:

- Built infrastructure
- Green infrastructure
- Urban green spaces

Built and green infrastructure have a (multi-)functional connotation whereas urban green spaces are considered to have a structural connotation – they are the structural components of green infrastructure. Typologies of urban green spaces are usually distinguished in structural and/or functional classification approaches (Maes et al., 2016). For mapping and assessment of urban ecosystems and their services, they provide indicators on three scales:

- Regional scale
- Metropolitan scale (functional urban area, FUA)
- Urban scale (core area of the FUA, “city”)

Maes et al. (2016) provide a list of key ecosystem services regarding relevance in urban areas. In terms of *provisioning services* they consider provision of food and water as those with most importance in cities; regarding *cultural services* these are nature based recreation and education, and cultural heritage. As main providers of cultural ecosystem services in urban areas, Maes et al. (2016, p. 88) name “urban forests, crop fields, fruit trees, private and public gardens, parks and playgrounds, fresh water bodies, and coastal and marine ecosystems”. Furthermore, protected areas such as Natura 2000 need to be considered.

2.4 Ecosystem services and tourism

Recreation and tourism are considered as cultural ecosystem services, however, according to the CICES framework it is understood only as “*physical and intellectual interaction with the environment*” (Kulczyk, Woźniak, Kowalczyk, & Derek, 2014, p. 85). Based on a semi-quantitative literature review on **cultural services**, Milcu et al. (2013) identified 11 subcategories of cultural services:

- Recreation and ecotourism
- Aesthetic values
- Spiritual and religious values
- Educational values
- Cultural heritage values
- Bequest, intrinsic and existence
- Inspiration
- Sense of place
- Knowledge systems
- Social relations
- Cultural diversity

The list mostly relates to non-material benefits (Egoh Benis, Drakou, Dunbar Martha, Maes, & Willemen, 2012). Besides 'recreation and ecotourism', many of the above-mentioned cultural services can be considered as relevant for tourism (e.g. aesthetic values, culture heritage). This is also confirmed by Hernández-Morcillo et al. (2013). They mention, for example, spiritual sites such as churches can be considered both as places of spiritual value and as touristic sites. This exemplifies that sites or elements of ecosystems can provide multiple services.

One of the few projects dealing with the nexus between ecosystem services and tourism is "Tourism, Wellbeing and Ecosystem Services" (TObeWELL, 2015). Part of the project was the development of a research tool, based on a questionnaire, "to empirically value the benefits of visited landscapes for tourists and visitors". The tool can be used for comparing landscapes as well as assessing trends and evaluating effects of landscape changes. (Smith & Ram, 2017, p. 116 f.)

Also Daniel et al. (2012) acknowledge the importance of *recreation and tourism*, such as walking, camping or nature study, as part of cultural ecosystem services and also its contributions to physical and psychological well-being, such as "*physical exercise, aesthetic experiences, intellectual stimulation, inspiration*" (Daniel et al., 2012, p. 8814). However, recreation and tourism are at the same time considered as a threat to ecosystems through, e.g., "*wildlife disturbance and habitat fragmentation [...] and negative offsite effects are commonly attributed to traffic emissions and infrastructure developments for tourism*" (Daniel et al., 2012, p. 8814).

According to Willis (2015) natural resources provide an important condition for enhancement in psychological well-being. Willis suggests that cultural ecosystem services can "*be understood in terms of ecosystems' contributions to benefits which are argued to be the constituents of psychological well-being*" (Willis, 2015, p. 40). This starting point is very relevant for discussing the role of nature in tourism or tourists' experiences. On the one hand, because it helps understanding tourists' motivations for visiting certain places and, on the other hand, because it implies the need to maintain those natural resources (Willis, 2015), which – considering the threat of tourism on ecosystems (Daniel et al., 2012) calls for sustainable tourism strategies.

In this sense, understanding how ecosystem services contribute to touristic experiences fosters engaging in practices related to sustainable tourism, such as reduction of waste generation and improving waste management, in order to preserve those contributing services.

3 Ecosystem service approach in URBAN WASTE

In this deliverable, we focus on ecosystem services and tourism, as tourism is a core theme of URBAN WASTE. Recreation and tourism are part of cultural ecosystems services in the CICES classification (EEA, 2017a). However, the literature also considers most other cultural ecosystems services as relevant for tourism as they are for example defined in Milcu et al. (2013). Furthermore, following Maes et al. (2013), we consider provisioning services as water and food, as they are directly relevant for tourism. For the subsequent work, we will therefore focus on the following ecosystem services:

- Provisioning services
 - Provision of local freshwater
 - Provision of local food
- Cultural services
 - Recreation and ecotourism
 - Aesthetics / beauty
 - Spiritual / religious meaning
 - Learning and teaching
 - Cultural heritage
 - Inspiration, Sense of place

Mapping and assessment of urban ecosystem services is yet not sufficiently developed and only few studies address urban ecosystems at all. As all pilot cases in URBAN WASTE are – at least to a certain extent – urban areas, this research gap is a challenge for our work. We will therefore approach the topic from three perspectives, providing insights for each city:

1. **Tourist perspective:** Analysis of the additional ecosystem service questions in the tourist **survey** done in URBAN WASTE's WP3 (de Luca et al., 2017)
2. **Good examples:** Providing **factsheets of good examples** of ecosystem services from the URBAN WASTE pilot cities, based on a discussion with city partners at the Copenhagen meeting
3. **Quantitative benchmark:** Analysis of **indicators** describing the state of the spatial environment in the URBAN WASTE pilot cities. The benchmark as such does not evaluate ecosystem services, but evaluates the ecosystem conditions, which is also suggested as a feasible way for assessment by Maes et al. (2016). The chosen indicators can be described as proxies for the state of the spatial environment (with relevance for tourism) in the pilot cases. Three aspects are covered
 - Built environment
 - Touristic features
 - Nature areas

Besides the choice of the indicators, the selection of the spatial scale is crucial for such a benchmark. Instead of using the very diverse administrative boundaries, we use a 10 km radius from the urban centre of the cities to enhance comparability and account for locally relevant ecosystem services. Figure 3 illustrates the 10 km radius delineation and the administrative boundaries of the pilot cases.

Figure 3: Case boundary and 10 km radius from city centre

4 Tourists' and tourist workers' ranking of ecosystem services in the pilot cities

Between mid-November 2016 and mid-January 2017 three surveys targeting waste workers, tourist workers and tourists were conducted in all 11 pilot cities. The surveys, coordinated by WP3, focus on waste management and behaviour/attitudes. Additionally, we added two questions regarding ecosystem services in the tourist workers- and tourists-survey. Details on the survey methods and results can be found in Deliverable 3.2 (de Luca et al., 2017) and in a forthcoming research paper (Große et al., 2018).

Figure 4: Responses per city and survey

Tourists and tourist workers were asked to rate the importance of the following ecosystem services on a three-fold scale (“Very Important ... Somehow important ... Not important”):

- Provision of local freshwater
- Provision of local food
- Recreation and ecotourism
- Aesthetics / beauty
- Spiritual / religious meaning
- Learning and teaching
- Cultural heritage
- Inspiration, Sense of place

Table 1: Top 4-Ecosystem Services ranked as “very important” by tourists and tourist workers

	Tourists				Tourist workers			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Copenhagen					Less than 10 responses			
Dubrovnik								
Florence								
Kavala								
Lisbon								
Nice								
Nicosia								
Ponta Delgada								
Santander								
Syracuse								
Tenerife								

Legend

Freshwater	Provision of local food	Recreation and eco-tourism	Aesthetics / beauty	Spiritual / religious meaning	Learning and teaching	Cultural heritage	Inspiration, Sense of place	Other (tourist survey only)

Almost in all cities and in both surveys, the following three are in the **Top 4**:

- Freshwater provision
- Local food provision
- Cultural heritage

Other ecosystem services seem to be relevant only in some cases, as spiritual / religious meaning and learning in Florence and Syracuse. Even recreation and ecotourism are only ranked in some cities into the Top 4. In a study of the perception of cultural ecosystem services from Germany (Plieninger, Dijks, Oteros-Rozas, & Bieling, 2013), recreation (split into various subcategories) was mentioned as the most important service. The difference in our survey might be caused from having only one category for recreation. Aesthetics, social relations and educational values rank second in the German study, while spiritual services, sense of place, cultural heritage and inspiration rank lowest. Another explanation could be the different motivation of tourist to visit a place, where particular sights can play a big role additionally to general aspects of recreation.

Tourist and tourist workers were also asked to give examples for those ES they rated as “very important” (e.g. name of an area, name of a product, name of a resource, type of usage). Table 2 shows a summary of the answers. The answers were used for the selection of examples of ecosystem services (see chapter 5).

Table 2: Suggestions for ES cases (from survey and previous discussions) – answers were given in different languages and translated, if necessary, with the help of Google Translate

City	ES case
Copenhagen	Harbour or the old fortification – urban/water ecosystem, tourist site (little mermaid), bathing Amager Strandpark
Dubrovnik	<p>“Dubrovnik, Ombla river source of fresh water in danger because Grabovica junk yard a few miles away. Local original sorts of wine like Plavac mali, Malvasija, Posip etc. Local olive oil, Ston OYSTERS, figs... Cultural heritage, monuments, folklor, a capella singing...”</p> <p>“Availability of drinking water Dubrovnik - drinking water from the fountain, Esterik, the beauty of the purity streets of the city - all the public areas, especially the more attention given green space, clean sea and beaches, organization. Recreation and ecotourism - sufficient offer sdrzaja for all age groups. Local culinary specialties - strive to be in the hundreds of restaurants offer more authentic dishes - exploring culture and utilization of local growers and producers - as well as the diversity of offers. Cultural heritage - getting to know the local history of the place / city. Inspiration - a sense of place - impressions of touch with local people - hospitality and service workers.”</p>
Florence	<p>City centre, public free fresh water for tourists and citizens</p> <p>“Tuscany is really rich of tremendously good local food such as meat, cheese and vegetables. The landscape in the surrounding is really worth the trip.</p> <p>Tuscany life style; Florence city of culture and world heritage, the beauty of the old town</p>

	<p>Tourists can be sensitive to the services that affect his health</p> <p>The historic centre of Florence UNESCO Heritage Site: The urban complex of Florence is in itself a unique artistic achievement, a masterpiece, the result of continuous time creating six centuries. Here we find, besides the museums, the strongest concentration of d 'art known throughout the world. From the fifteenth century, Florence exerted a 'dominant influence on the development of architecture and monumental arts, first in Italy and then in Europe. The artistic principles of the Renaissance have been defined since 1400 by Brunelleschi, Donatello and Masaccio. It is within the Florentine realities that have formed and established two geni-uses: Michelangelo and Leonardo da Vinci. The historic centre of Florence brings an excep-tional testimony, both as merchant cities of the Middle Ages and of the Renaissance city. Flor-ence has preserved intact streets, fortified palaces Lodges, fountains, Ponte Vecchio. The trades, organized into guilds, have left several monuments. Numerous palaces, from the four-teenth to the seventeenth century, are testimony to the power attained by Principles and bankers E 'during the period of the Neo-Platonic Academy that was forged the concept of Humanism and the Renaissance."</p>
Kavala	<p>some island (forgot name) close to Kavala which gets many tourists</p> <p>"the water must be protected as free and pure products from all the food can move up throughout the area and let the travellers a unique experience that will make them to return or to recommend to others the area nobody I want to face rubbish bin extracts, dirty, abandoned cities, even if the economic crisis in the region."</p>
Lisbon	<p>"buy fresh food on the market"</p> <p>"Historic area of Lisbon"</p> <p>"Tap water from the city of Lisbon, protected areas in Lisbon (Monsanto, Sintra, Arrábida, ...)."</p>
Nice	<p>"Mediterranean sea"</p>
Nicosia	<p>"Local fresh water - provided all over the city in the form of dispensers</p> <p>Local food - restaurants and other food providers should be encouraged to include in their menus local food options for the visitor to appreciate the local gastronomy and culture of our country. Examples: tzatziki, xoriatiki salada, kouloumbra, kolokasi, koupepia, pourgouri, hal-loumi, kappama, traditional sweets such as karydaki, soutzoukko, halva</p> <p>Recreation and eco-tourism - visitors should be given the opportunity to visit natural areas that conserve the environment and sustain the well-being of the local people. The idea here is to build environmental and cultural awareness and respect as well as provide positive experi-ences for the visitors.</p> <p>Cultural heritage - Ecotourism adds value to cultural traditions and practices. As the world becomes westernized, traditional dances, festivals, methods for preparing food, or storing water may become obsolete. The way ecotourism functions to preserve traditional life certain-ly does not aim to impede progress. Instead, it offers incentives to keep tradition alive and to preserve the heritage of a culture, village, or country because eco-tourists are willing to learn about such things.</p> <p>CONCLUSION: There is an urgent need to locate private and public initiatives, bring them to-</p>

	<p>gether under a suitable means of communication such as a web platform in order to give visitors (and locals) a variety of options to choose from.”</p>
Ponta Delgada	<p>“we searched out restaurants in Ponta Delgada e Funchal that served local food. we visited churches furnas hot springs, hikes on islands of madeira local market in Funchal, gardens in Ponta Delgada” [probably cruise tourists who visited Funchal/Madeira and Ponta Delgada/Azores]</p> <p>“Termalpool Caldeiras das Furnas”</p> <p>“lagoa de fogo”</p> <p>“Vista do Rei - Sete Cidades Azores Trails”</p> <p>“The main attraction of the Azores is nature in general. Much more than culture, religion, etc.”</p> <p>“Extreme activities (in contact with nature). Local religion and all movements.”</p> <p>“Leisure activities such as whale watching, mountain biking, etc.”</p>
Santander	<p>“Parque de la vaguada de Las Llamas”</p>
Syracuse	<p>Nature protection area close to city (about 10 km)</p> <p>“wine production - importance of protected areas (Ciane, Saline, Plemmirio)”</p> <p>“Provision of local freshwater WOULD be important, but unfortunately tap water from Siracusa cannot be considered (or offered to tourists) as drinking water. So much plastic for bottled water could be safe if tap water was truly drinking water.</p> <p>Food is one of the main reasons tourists visit our area, luckily almost all produce is grown locally.</p> <p>Recreation and ecotourism WOULD be important to the area, but practically inexistent.</p> <p>Aesthetics/beauty - the area is so beautiful by itself, unfortunately that beauty is very often spoilt with garbage along the roads.</p> <p>Cultural heritage is the main reason people visit this area, too many to mention. Unfortunately also those areas are often cluttered with garbage!”</p>
Tenerife	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - El Teide national park + heritage site - Anaga Biosphere Reserve - 43 protected areas in the Canary Island Network + 56 conservation areas (natura 2000) <p>“trekking ecoturismo”</p> <p>“The Canary Islands need always freshwater, half of them are almost desert.”</p>

5 Examples of ecosystem services related to tourism in the pilot cities

In this section, we exemplify various relevant ecosystems services by cases from the pilot cities, describing a selected (urban) ecosystem, the relevant services of it for tourism, and how we evaluate its effects in a wider understanding. The examples were chosen based on comments given by respondents of the tourist and tourist staff surveys (see Table 2) and by URBAN WASTE project partners during the meeting in Copenhagen in May 2017 (Figure 5). The selection does not provide a comprehensive picture of ecosystem services in the pilot cities, but illustrates the variety of different types of ecosystem services related to tourism.

Figure 5: Discussing ecosystem services in the 11 cases at the Copenhagen meeting, 31 May 2017

5.1 La Coulée Verte (Nice)

<p>La Coulée Verte (Nice)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p><i>La Coulée Verte</i> ('the green stream') is a green infrastructure in the centre of Nice, following a former riverbed from the Northeast of the city to its very centre at the coast. Its core are gardens and pedestrian space. Its second name, <i>Promenade du Paillon</i>, refers to the river Paillon, which was covered in several stages from around 1860 and onwards. The final stage was first completed after the Second World War. In the 1970s/80s a bus terminal and a parking deck were established, closing the former open space. In 2010, demolition and restructuring began. In 2013, the new green infrastructure was inaugurated.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p><i>La Coulée Verte</i> is an important element of the city's green structure and contributes significantly to its aesthetical and recreational value. It is an important place for outdoor recreation in the city and includes playgrounds and picnic areas. The area is also composed of 1,600 trees, 6,000 shrubs and 50,000 perennials as well as 3,000 m² of different water surfaces, mitigating urban heat island effects. In addition, real estate prices increased around the area.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The area is connecting parts of the city centre with the coast in an area very attractive for tourists. Some tourist attractions are part of the green infrastructure, e.g. the Garden Albert 1st, the Modern and Contemporary Art Museum, the National Theatre of Nice or the Nice Acropolis, a congress and exhibition centre. <i>La Coulée Verte</i> thereby supports soft ways of transport (walking, biking etc.) between these points of interests and the connected areas.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city</i></p>	<p>The city with the region were the main actors in the process of implementing <i>La Coulée Verte</i>, which cost EUR 40 million. The city is also responsible for the maintenance of the gardens.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching (schools close by can use it) Cultural heritage</p>	
<p>Source: https://lacouleevertence.wordpress.com, https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Promenade_du_Paillon</p>		

5.2 Area Marine Plemmirio & bike route (Syracuse)

<p>Area Marine Plemmirio & bike route (Syracuse)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The Marine protection area Plemmirio is located on the east coast, south west of Syracuse. It is classified as a “Specially Protected Area of Mediterranean Importance”. The area is an important habitat for flora and fauna, but has also historical importance, e.g. shipwrecks from Ancient up to Modern times can be found here.</p> <p>There is a mountain bike path along the coast around the peninsula and a bike lane in the interior. Furthermore, a 7 km bike route from Syracuse city centre connects the area.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The Plemmirio area is very close to Syracuse and an important area for recreation. However, the close location to the urban area also puts the area under high development pressure, which can be a challenge for the city.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The seabed is very rich in any marine species populating the Mediterranean and a popular place for diving. The protection area status raises tourists’ awareness of the importance of nature conservation and ecosystem services. The paths allow the exploration of the area by foot and bike.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The city of Syracuse and the province of Syracuse are entrusted by the Ministry of Environment to manage and maintain the area.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Provision of local food Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching (schools close by can use it) Cultural heritage</p>	
<p>Source: http://www.parks.it/riserva.marina.plemmirio/Eindex.php, http://www.plemmirio.it</p>		

5.3 Harbour Park and Harbour Circle (Copenhagen)

<p>Harbour park (Copenhagen)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The Harbour Park (Islands Brygge Havneparken) is centrally located in Copenhagen. The park is located on a former industrial harbour site. The site got slowly deindustrialized in the 1970. In 1983, the local association of residence overtook part of the site, establishing a first park in 1984. As the park became very popular over the years, the municipality overtook the maintenance of the park in 1994. In the following years, the park was redesigned and officially opened in 2001. The park is also a core open space of the Copenhagen inner and southern harbour which became an attractive space for recreation in the past decade, connected by several walking/cycling bridges to other parts of the city by the “Harbour Circle route”</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>In the first years, the park was at the core of the identity of the local neighbourhood, a community project. Since, it became one of the most popular outdoor spaces in the city and an important city brand. The transformation of the harbour also included several measures to increase the water quality so that it was possible to establish a harbour bath.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>With its central location, the harbour park is also attractive for tourists. Besides that, the park and the whole harbour are well connected by walking/cycling bridges, allowing tourist to take bike, walk or run tours around the whole harbour (Harbour Circle route)</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The municipality of Copenhagen is the main planning authority and maintaining the park.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Provision of local food (improvement of water quality in the harbour, thereby improving fishing ground) Recreation and ecotourism Aesthetics / beauty Cultural heritage (elements of industrial heritage kept and transformed)</p>	
<p>Source: http://www.kobenhavnergron.dk/place/havneparken, http://www.visitcopenhagen.com/harbourcircle</p>		

5.4 Archaeological Site of Philippi (Kavala)

<p>Archaeological Site of Philippi (Kavala)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The Archaeological Site of Philippi is located about 15 km northwest of the centre of Kavala. It has been nominated as UNESCO World Heritage in 2016 following the joint efforts of the Greek Ministry of Culture and the Municipality of Kavala. Philippi are the remains of a walled city adjacent to an acropolis dating back to 360 BC. It is considered one of the most important and complete archaeological sites in northern Greece. The archaeological site stretches across an area of relevant ecological interest in terms of natural environment and geomorphology. It covers an area of 87.545 ha and a buffer zone of 176.291 ha.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>Philippi is one out of 18 UNESCO World Heritage sites in Greece, a considerable touristic sight for visitors of Kavala and the surroundings and is part of representing and preserving the Greek identity and cultural heritage.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>As attractor for tourists, it also contributes to economic interests of the city and the region. Philippi is located in an area of ecological interest, its conservation as archaeological site benefits therefore likewise the conservation of the natural environment and might help raising awareness in terms of respectful and sensitive tourism.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The nomination of Philippi as UNESCO World Heritage is the result of a joint effort of the Greek Ministry of Culture and the Municipality of Kavala. It is managed at the local level by the Ephorate of Antiquities, the Regional Service of the General Directorate of Antiquities and Cultural Heritage, within the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching Cultural heritage Inspiration, Sense of place</p>	
<p>Source: http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1517/; Hellenic Republic (2015), Nomination for inscription on the World Heritage List</p>		

5.5 Historic city centre (Florence)

<p>Historic city centre (Florence)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The historic city centre of Florence is not a specific nature or green urban area as many of the other examples. However, we anyway decided to take it in as an example for an urban ecosystem as the balance between providing quality of life for the citizens, satisfying touristic demand and protecting the cultural heritage is a similar challenge in many of the other cases. The city centre was declared world heritage by the UNESCO in 1982. With its unique historical built-up structure and the concentration of art objects, it is known as the "cradle of the Renaissance".</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The protection of the historical city centre provides a local identity of a rich cultural heritage for the citizens. However, protection, as always, can also be a barrier to (necessary) improvements, which the city needs to tackle in other ways to keep living affordable in the centre.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>Florence is one of the many touristic cities in Italy. The conservation of the historic structure and the exhibition of many art objects of cultural historical importance can sensitize visitors for a responsible behaviour with their own cultural heritage.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>Since 2006, the Municipality has adopted a Management Plan for the Historic Centre of Florence. In the city's Master Plan, Florence identifies the historic centre as a place of cultural and environmental concern. Only conservation and restoration practices are put into action. It foresees improving living conditions for residents, tourism, and initiatives to increase awareness of the historic centre as a World Heritage property. Associated with this initiative is a building policy, which controls activities in the historic centre.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching Cultural heritage Inspiration, Sense of place</p>	
<p>Source: http://www.firenzepatrimoniomondiale.it/en/piano-di-gestione, http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/174</p>		

5.6 City walls (Nicosia)

<p>City walls (Nicosia)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The defensive Venetian city walls surround the city of Nicosia at a length of ca. 4.8 km. Formed as a circle, they include 11 bastions and three gates. As the walls are still largely intact, they are among the best preserved Renaissance fortifications in the Eastern Mediterranean. The original walls date back to the Middle Ages, but were replaced in the mid-16th century by the Venetians.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The walls have significant importance as historical touristic site. Moreover, the moat surrounding the walls is nowadays used for diverse purposes, such as sports fields, public gardens, an open-air sculpture exhibition, but also car parks etc.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The walls of Nicosia are a unique landmark of the city that attracts tourists, represents the historical heritage of the city and the region, and is nowadays an important local recreational area used by the citizens and visitors.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The contiguous urban area of Nicosia stretches far beyond the walls which are located in the centre of the city. Due to the political situation, the walls are located partly in the administrative area of Northern Nicosia, partly in the area of Southern Nicosia (Republic of Cyprus) and partly in the UN buffer zone.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching Cultural heritage Inspiration, Sense of place</p>	
<p>Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Walls_of_Nicosia; www.nicosia.org.cy/en-GB/discover/sights/the-medieval-walls/</p>		

5.7 Nature trails (Ponta Delgada)

<p>Nature trails (Ponta Delgada)</p>	<p>(left: Vista do Rei, right: Lagoa do Fogo; source: Wikimedia Commons)</p>		<p>(source: Google Earth)</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The volcanic archipelago of the Azores provides a net of nature hiking trails that are traditional footpaths used to travel within the islands, to move cattle to and from pastures or for transporting agricultural products, fish, charcoal and other merchandise for trade. This network of footpaths has been restored and made accessible for visitors.</p> <p>The two roots <i>Vista do Rei - Sete Cidades</i> and <i>Praia – Lagoa do Fogo</i>, about 20 km west and 25 km east, respectively, of Ponta Delgada are almost entirely located within areas classified as Protected Landscape or Natural Reserve.</p>		
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The nature trails of the Azores combine places of historical importance with nature preservation and recreational and touristic purposes.</p>		
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The nature trails are a unique example of a touristic attraction that promotes sustainable tourism and raises awareness for nature protection at the same time. Hiking and outdoor experience are the main touristic purposes for visiting the Azores, it is therefore of inherent importance to protect the natural heritage, which is most likely similarly perceived by the arriving tourists and might help to promote environmental awareness of the visitors and locals.</p>		
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The management of the nature trails and the classification of the areas on types of protected areas underlie the Regional Government of the Azores.</p>		
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Freshwater Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching Cultural heritage</p>		
<p>Source: http://trails.visitazores.com/en/trails-azores</p>			

5.8 Parque de la Vaguada de las Llamas (Santander)

<p>Parque de la Vaguada de las Llamas (Santander)</p>	<p>(source: Google Earth)</p>		
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The Parque de la Vaguada de Las Llamas is located along the La Vaguada de las Llamas, which runs along the extent of the peninsula of Santander to Sardinero Beach at the Atlantic Ocean. In the course of the touristic development of Santander in the 19th century the marshy estuary was filled, the natural drainage interrupted and the tidal flow blocked which turned the area into a run-down garbage ground and damaged its ecosystem.</p> <p>The Municipality of Santander obtained the land back from private owners and initiated an environmental recovery urban park project in 2006, which today forms the main green space of the city with a size of 11 ha..</p>		
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>As an ecological recovery project the Parque de la Vaguada de las Llamas plays an important role as a local ecosystem, as “green lung” of the city and as recreational space for citizens and visitors,</p>		
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The urban park is probably not a main reason for visiting Santander but can play an important role in awareness raising regarding ecological quality as well as it increases the overall quality of Santander as a touristic destination. It provides furthermore a striking example for how to reverse the ecological failures of the past.</p>		
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The recovery project was carried out by the Municipality of Santander who obtained the private properties where the park is located.</p>		
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty</p>		
<p>Source: www.publicspace.org/en/works/e153-parque-atlantico-en-la-vaguada-de-las-llamas-fase-1; https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Parque_de_la_vaguada_de_Las_Llamas; https://santanderspain.info/</p>			

5.9 Beaches and urban parks (Puerto de la Cruz, Tenerife)

<p>Beaches / Urban parks (Puerto de la Cruz, Tenerife)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>A unique feature of Tenerife is its diversity in types of landscapes across different regions and altitudes of the island, which are related to considerable differences in the micro-climate. However, the island is part of the sub-tropical climate zone, the southern part is located in the rain shadow and therefore the warmer and drier, whereas the northern part receives most of the rainfalls, resulting in more “green” flora.</p> <p>Puerto de la Cruz at the north coast represents a combination of the natural diversity of the island that combine beaches and a variety of gardens, such as a botanical garden (Jardín de Aclimatación de La Orotava or “Botánico”)and the Sitio Litre Orchid Garden, both established already in the 18th century, the Risco Belle Aquatic Gardens and Parque Taoro.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The Beaches and gardens of Puerto de la Cruz provide rich recreational features of the city for both citizens and visitors; the gardens contribute furthermore to preservation of ecological diversity and knowledge provision.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The unique diversity of landscapes, from beaches to mountains, is probably one of the main reasons for visiting Tenerife. Tourism is one of the main economic sectors of the Canary Islands, therefore keeping the balance of tourism and protecting the natural capital of Tenerife is a difficult challenge.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The botanical garden was originally established by the Spanish king. Responsibilities have shifted during the years; currently the Canary Island Government is maintaining it.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching</p>	
<p>Source: http://therealtenerife.com/posts/the-gardens-of-puerto-de-la-cruz, https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jard%C3%ADn_de_Aclimataci%C3%B3n_de_La_Orotava</p>		

5.10 Ombla river (Dubrovnik Neretva Region)

<p>Ombla river (Dubrovnik Neretva Region)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>The Ombla river is located about 5 km northeast of the centre of Dubrovnik and is only about 30 m long. It flows near Komolac into the Adriatic Sea.</p> <p>The river area is a Nationally Designated Area (CDDA) – Protected Landscape/Seascape - and the north adjacent area is a Natura 2000 Habitat Directive site.</p> <p>The Ombla river is since the late 19th century of high importance for Dubrovnik’s fresh water supply and in the future also for electricity generation by a planned hydroelectric power plant. In the past, many summer residences were located along the river.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>The current main relevance of the river is the fresh water supply for Dubrovnik. But the river has additionally high values as local recreational area as well as an ecosystem, especially in relation to the adjacent protected area.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The river itself is possibly not a major magnet for tourists coming to Dubrovnik and the Neretva Region. However, due to its protected status it helps protecting the area from the negative impacts of tourism and as such promotes sustainable tourism in the area around Dubrovnik.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The responsibility for the Ombla river is shared due to its multi-functionality as a fresh water supplier (City of Dubrovnik, municipal waterworks) and as a protected nature area (region, state).</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Freshwater Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty</p>	
<p>Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ombla; EEA 2017</p>		

5.11 Monsanto Forest Park (Lisbon)

<p>Monsanto Forest Park (Lisbon)</p>	<p>(Source: Google Earth)</p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>Monsanto Forest Park (Parque Florestal de Monsanto) is a forested park covering an area of about 800 ha located in the Monsanto hills west of Lisbon centre.</p> <p>Until the 1930s the area was intensively used for agriculture which led to substantial erosion. The re-plantation of the park was initiated in 1934. About 50 ha of the park are partly fenced and especially protected – the Ecological Park – as it is home to specific animal species.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for Quality of Life</i></p>	<p>Monsanto Forest Park provides besides its important function as a “green lung” and ecological habitat of the city an important recreational area for citizens and visitors of Lisbon. The park includes diverse leisure areas, such as sports fields, biking and walking trails or picnic areas.</p>	
<p><i>Relevance for (sustainable) tourism</i></p>	<p>The park itself is possibly not one of the main attractions for tourists to visit Lisbon. It is, however, an important oasis for residents and visitors and promotes soft tourism due to its natural character.</p>	
<p><i>The role of the city/region</i></p>	<p>The initiation of the reforestation and re-plantation of the park was effected by a Portuguese Secretary of State for the Public Works in the 1930s.</p> <p>Today the park is owned and managed by the Municipality of Lisbon.</p>	
<p><i>Classification of ecosystem services</i></p>	<p>Recreation and eco-tourism Aesthetics / beauty Learning and teaching Inspiration, Sense of place</p>	
<p>Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Monsanto_Forest_Park; www.visitlisboa.com/see-do/sightseeing-activities/nature-adventure/monsanto-forest-park; www.lisbon-tourism.com/en/lisbon-attractions/parks-and-gardens-in-lisbon/monsanto-forest-park.html; www.cm-lisboa.pt/en/living-in/environment/monsanto-forest-park</p>		

6 The spatial environment in the pilot cities

In this chapter, we return to the city scale. We do not assess urban ecosystem services directly, but conduct a benchmark of the cities' state of environment based on various European and global datasets. The benchmark illustrates the diversity of situations where tourism and environmental features meet in an urban context and allows a, very general though, comparison of the current situation in the pilot cases – and therewith the extent of potential action. Results from this work can be used in the work on strategies (WP4 – e.g. How can selected ecosystem services be used to improve tourism and waste management, or which impacts on selected ecosystem services should be considered when developing strategies) and impact assessment (WP7).

Taking a closer look at the spatial character of the cities is important. Many different features can occur in different areas of a city. For example, in terms of tourism in the 11 pilot cases of the URBANWASTE project, we can imagine that some areas are significantly more attractive for, or affected by, tourism than other areas in the same city. This could include historical centres, coastal areas and beaches or nature areas of special interest. Furthermore, generic spatial or geographical features of a city, such as urban density, land use or the extent of nature areas illustrate the general conditions for ecosystem services.

We provide an overview on the spatial environment of the pilot cities by looking at:

- Built environment (urban land use, transport infrastructure)
- Tourism and population (hotels and restaurants but also population density as proxy for urban attraction)
- Green infrastructure (nature and open space, coastal zones, protection sites)

We will summarise those with a few key indicators in 'spatial environment profiles' for each city and group them according to the spatial context. Before that, we will shortly describe the spatial delineation and the data used for the analysis.

6.1 Spatial delineation and data sources

Different territorial authorities in URBAN WASTE represent the pilot cities: municipalities, counties, metropolitan areas. Most data collected in other parts of URBAN WASTE work package 2 refers to these entities. Ecosystems, however, do not follow local administrative boundaries hardly do touristic activities. We are fully aware that political action or policy is dependent on these boundaries; however, for this analysis we chose to give priority to the comparative perspective. We therefore use the area within a 10 km radius from the city centre for data analysis, which improves general possibilities for comparison across diverse cases as well as of environmental features more particular. Figure 3 (see chapter 3 , page 10) shows both delineations for all cases, whereas Tenerife is represented in three sub-cases (Arona, Adeje and Puerto de la Cruz).

We use freely available data from different sources, covering all cities. This includes data from the European CORINE Land Cover database (EEA, 2016), Eurostat's population grid (Eurostat, 2012) and OpenStreetMap (Geofabrik, 2017). The data is spatially explicit, that means the location (coordinates) of features are known - not just on an aggregate level as e.g. the postcode or the municipality as a whole. This information makes it possible to illustrate them on maps to show spatial differences, identify hotspots and describe the spatial character.

6.2 Built environment

The pilot cities of URBAN WASTE are represented by very diverse administrative settings. This becomes clear when we compare the population within the administrative area and the population within a 10 km radius. Lisbon is the only case with more than 1 million inhabitants within 10 km radius, followed by Copenhagen with almost 0.9 million. Florence and Nice have each around 0.5 million, Santander and Nicosia 250.000. The smallest cities are Dubrovnik, Kavala and Ponta Delgada. Looking at the population in relation to the amount of urban area (opposite to nature, water etc.) changes the picture slightly (Figure 6). E.g. Puerto de la Cruz has almost the same population density as Lisbon, while Adeje, which is also characterized by much tourist infrastructure, has the least density of resident population.

Table 3 Population and population density

Name	Population in pilot case area (municipality / region, most recent year)	Population within 10 km radius (2011)	Urban area within 10 km radius (2012)	Population density per urban area within 10 km radius
Adeje*	46.667	94.012	127	739
Arona*	79.890	122.547	74	1.654
Puerto de la Cruz*	29.435	141.971	19	7.288
Santander	172.656	257.844	50	5.179
Ponta Delgada	68.809	72.688	25	2.922
Copenhagen	580.295	879.424	167	5.259
Nice Metro	536.327	472.373	100	4.734
Lisbon	504.471	1.131.261	148	7.651
Florence	378.174	508.408	80	6.383
Syracuse	122.503	112.943	35	3.265
Dubrovnik Neretva	122.568	48.214	16	3.099
Kavala	70.501	66.034	17	3.862
Nicosia	55.014	240.989	122	1.982

Data source: Pilot city partners, EEA 2016 and Eurostat 2012

* The three municipalities of Adeje, Arona and Puerto de la Cruz belong to the pilot case Tenerife.

Figure 6: Population and urban population density within 10 km radius

The city with the highest share of urban area within a 10 km radius from the city centre is Copenhagen, with more than half of the area urbanized, followed by Lisbon, Adeje and Nicosia. Nice, Florence and Arona have a medium share of urban areas, while Santander and Syracuse are in the lower half. Ponta Delgada, Puerto de la Cruz, Kaval and Dubrovnik are the cities with the lowest share of urban area within 10 km radius. In around half of the cities, water areas (including the sea) cover half of the area within 10 km. Florence and Nicosia stand out in this comparison as they are highly urbanized but still have high shares of open land (agriculture, nature) because of their inland location. The spatial distribution of land use in the URBANWASTE pilot cases is shown in Figure 8.

Table 4: Land use in 2012, in 10 km radius from centre, km2

Name (sorted by urban area)	Total (km ²)	water	Total land	urban	other	agriculture	nature (incl. urban green)
Copenhagen	314	92	223	167	8	12	35
Lisbon	314	122	193	148	6	19	19
Adeje*	314	73	241	127	5	34	76
Nicosia	314	1	313	122	7	138	47
Nice	314	107	207	100	1	25	81
Florence	314	3	312	80	3	170	60
Arona*	314	204	110	74	3	30	3
Santander	314	150	164	50	5	90	20
Syracuse	314	188	126	35	1	76	14
Ponta Delgada	314	165	149	25	3	111	10
Puerto de la Cruz*	314	133	181	19	1	69	91
Kavala	314	127	187	17	1	67	102
Dubrovnik	314	164	150	16	2	19	113

Data source: EEA, 2016

* The three municipalities of Adeje, Arona and Puerto de la Cruz belong to the pilot case Tenerife.

Figure 7: Land use 2012, share

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of land use in 2012 (Adeje, Arona and Puerto de la Cruz belong to Tenerife)

6.3 Tourism and population

The spatial distribution of the touristic features is often concentrated in few locations. As indicators for potentially high touristic activity we looked into the spatial distribution of hotels (and similar accommodation), food places as restaurants and population. The latter can be a proxy for touristic attraction (because many other functions might be available in dense urban areas); however, in some historic sites or also pure tourist areas, population density might be low. Figure 9 shows the area in each pilot case with potentially high tourist activity¹, i.e. the area with at least 10 hotels per km², or 10 food places per km², or 5000 inhabitants per km². The big cities as Lisbon and Copenhagen, but also Florence and Nice have big areas with many restaurants and population. Opposite to that, Adeje and Arona have a similar big areas with many hotels and restaurants, though only small area with dense population.

Figure 9: Area with potentially high tourist activity

In all cases, hotels are highly concentrated, food places a bit less while population is typically more spread, as shown in Figure 10. The steeper the curve, the higher is the spatial concentration. Most hotels and similar touristic accommodations are concentrated in a very small area. In almost all cases, 50 % of all hotels within a 10 km radius are located in an area of 4 km² (2 x 2 km), which is only 1-4 % of the cases land area. This is also illustrated by the maps in Figure 11. Copenhagen has, despite being a big city this sample, an extreme concentration of hotels. 25 % of all hotels (35 locations) are concentrated within 1 km². Restaurants and other food places are also concentrated around similar areas. Only in the bigger cities, those places are spread over a wider area. Population is also concentrated, but in general to a lesser degree than hotels and restaurants. Again, the

¹ The basis of this is location data of hotels, restaurants etc. from OpenStreetMap (Geofabrik 2017) aggregated to 1 km² grid cells. For each cell (= square kilometre) we therefore have the number of different features occurring as well as the population number, derived from Eurostat (2012)

bigger cities (Lisbon, Copenhagen, and Florence) are less concentrated on that scale than the others. Some places as e.g. Kavala are rather small and with only few touristic features.

Figure 10: Spatial concentration of hotels, restaurants and population within 10 km radius (314 km²) of the pilot cities

Figure 11: Areas with minimum 10 hotels of 10 food places per km²

6.4 Green infrastructure

Well-functioning nature areas are the backbone of ecosystem services. Just as with urban areas, definitions of nature areas can vary. Some might define it strictly as wilderness; others include man-made areas as for example urban parks. The examples in chapter 5 also include a wide range of such areas, ranging from the marine protection area just outside of Syracuse to the Forest Park inside Lisbon and the urban green band structure in the centre of Nice. Based on the available data we look into three types of areas: Nature areas as defined by the CORINE land cover survey (EEA, 2016), coastal areas² (EEA, 2015) and Natura 2000 protection areas (EEA, 2017b). Furthermore, we also include “Nationally designated areas (CDDA)” (EEA, 2017) which is the official source of protected area information from European countries to the World Database of Protected Areas (WDPA). Table 5 shows the area covered by these different types in each case city (in a 10 km radius).

Table 5: Nature, coastal and Natura 2000 areas in the URBAN WASTE pilot cases

Name sorted by nature area)	Nature areas, km ²	% of total land area	Coastal areas, km ²	% of total land area	Natura 2000 areas, km ²	% of total area	Nationally designated areas (CDDA), km ²	% of total land area
Dubrovnik-Ner.	113,0	76%	41,5	28%	49,0	16%	6,2	4%
Kavala	102,4	55%	23,5	13%	8,4	3%	40,1	21%
Puerto de la Cruz*	91,2	50%	22,7	13%	178,7	57%	85,1	47%
Nice	80,9	39%	28,9	14%	55,2	18%	9,9	5%
Adeje*	75,6	31%	20,9	9%	234,5	75%	99,4	41%
Florence	59,7	19%	0,0	0%	14,8	5%	4,7	2%
Nicosia	46,6	15%	0,0	0%	0,0	0%	8,9	3%
Copenhagen	35,0	16%	53,7	24%	28,8	9%	40,8	18%
Santander	19,7	12%	53,4	33%	15,2	5%	7,7	5%
Lisbon	19,5	10%	57,9	30%	53,4	17%	0,0	0%
Syracuse	14,5	11%	38,0	30%	23,3	7%	19,3	15%
Ponta Delgada	10,1	7%	32,9	22%	0,0	0%	1,9	1%
Arona*	2,9	3%	27,8	25%	101,5	32%	28,1	26%

Data sources: EEA 2015, 2016, 2017

* The three municipalities of Adeje, Arona and Puerto de la Cruz belong to the pilot case Tenerife.

The share of Natura 2000 areas is a ratio of the whole area (radius of 10 km = 314 km²) including water surfaces, as many Natura 2000 areas are actually marine protection areas. The other three types are calculate per land area only, i.e. the total area minus water surfaces (see also Table 4).

Figure 12 illustrates, that the cases contain nature areas of very different size and quality. The three Tenerife municipalities, Adeje, Puerto de la Cruz and Arona, have a relatively high share of protected areas in their proximity. This could indicate a highly vulnerable landscape, as all three cases are also tourist hot spots.

Another focus area are coastal zones. Almost half of the pilot cases have more than 25 % coastal zone, which typically area also important habitats, providing a range of ecosystem services.

² We defined coastal areas as a 1 km buffer inland from the actual coastline.

In some cases, nature areas, i.e. mainly forests but also other non-agricultural open space, cover quite a big share while only a part of it is protected – at least by those categories in the database. Especially Dubrovnik, Kvala and Nice have big nature areas in close proximity to the city compared to protected areas. These unprotected open areas might be most vulnerable to development pressure from increasing tourism. However, e.g. in the Dubrovnik-Neretva case, part of the 10 km area is located across the Croatian border in Bosnia-Herzegovina. The maps in Figure 13 also show this situation clearly. A review of protected (and non-protected) sites in terms of future tourism and development pressure could be a way to tackle this mismatch.

Figure 12: Share of different nature areas within 10 km from city centre

Figure 13: Nature and coastal areas and protected sites in the pilot cases

6.5 City profiles

Table 6: Key indicators of the spatial environment in the URBAN WASTE pilot cases (10 km radius from city centre)

Category	Built environment			Tourism and population			Green infrastructure		
	Urban area	Highways	Primary roads	Popula-tion	Hotels	Food places	Nature and open area	Coastal area	Natura 2000
Indicator ³									
unit	% of total land area	length in km		number			% of total land area		% of total area
Adeje*	53%	53	70	94,012	199	580	45%	9%	75%
Arona*	67%	56	66	122,547	198	632	30%	25%	32%
Copenhagen	75%	141	66	879,424	140	3,737	21%	24%	9%
Dubrovnik-Ner.	10%	-	38	48,214	82	228	88%	28%	16%
Florence	26%	127	107	508,408	245	894	74%	-	5%
Kavala	9%	55	30	66,034	13	86	90%	13%	3%
Lisbon	77%	380	180	1,131,261	277	2,259	20%	30%	17%
Nice	48%	108	116	472,373	196	702	51%	14%	18%
Nicosia	39%	164	127	240,989	27	277	59%	-	-
Ponta Delgada	17%	55	44	72,688	95	327	81%	22%	0%
Puerto de la Cruz*	11%	41	50	141,971	99	507	88%	13%	57%
Santander	30%	160	78	257,844	89	476	67%	33%	5%
Syracuse	27%	36	42	112,943	74	122	72%	30%	7%

Year of data: population data: 2011 (Eurostat 2016), urban and nature areas: 2012 (EEA 2016), roads, hotels, food places: 2017 (Geofabrik 2017), coast line: 2006 (EEA 2015)

* The three municipalities of Adeje, Arona and Puerto de la Cruz belong to the pilot case Tenerife.

Table 6 summarizes the spatial environment analysis of the URBAN WASTE pilot cases in nine key indicators. The spatial environment profiles presented in the following are a strong simplification of the situation, only based on the above 9 indicators. However, they allow for a general comparison of the spatial environment of the pilot cases. The indicators from Table 6 were standardized⁴ in order to see relative differences between them in each pilot case. The values do not necessarily mirror a good or bad situation, but simply illustrate different environmental situations. In a later step, e.g. in WP7, we should consider to update some of this data and identify trends and pressures on these environmental features.

Following the profiles, we grouped the cases in three types:

1. Pilot cases with high concentration of urban AND tourist infrastructure
2. Pilot cases with high concentration in SELECTED urban OR tourist infrastructure
3. Pilot cases with little concentration of urban and tourist infrastructure

³ It can be discussed if any denominator should be used, e.g. number of population or tourists. However, as we decided to harmonize the delineation of all cases by using a 10 km radius from the city centre, the cases are, from a spatial point of view, comparable with by actual numbers (e.g. length of highways, number of hotels, share of green space)

⁴ We use the z-score standardization, which transforms the indicators into standardized values with an average 0 and a standard deviation 1 and thereby keeps its metric information while allowing a comparison across different indicators.

The types thereby refer to the pressure on the environment to provide ecosystem services for the local and tourist population. Especially Lisbon stands out with, compared to the other cases, a high density of population and urban infrastructure as well as touristic infrastructure. Only little nature area is available within the 10 km radius despite its long coastline. The other cases in the first group have similar conditions, though less pronounced.

Figure 14: Group 1 - Pilot cases with high concentration of urban AND tourist infrastructure

The conditions for the environment in the other groups are different as can be seen in the different values of the three indicators related to the green infrastructure. The case with the highest share of nature and open space are cases with close rural hinterland including Kavala, Dubrovnik, Ponta Delgada, Syracuse but also Puerto de la Cruz, which, because of its location between coast and mountain has only relatively little area to be urbanised. The three cities on Tenerife, Puerto de la Cruz, Adeje and Arona are also the cities with the highest shares of Natura 2000 areas which, especially in the case of the two latter one is an important feature in the light of the high pressure from tourism development.

Regarding a more general conclusion from the profiles, we could summarize that in Group 1 the strategy could be to focus on the few but important environmental features inside the dense urban area. In Group 2 broad environmental features can still be preserved, while in Group 3, potential future development pressure needs to be identified to secure a balanced development not reducing existing and potential future ecosystem services. However, this grouping is only based on the few indicators, while many other aspects relevant in the project (e.g. waste production and treatment, governance structures) were not looked at in this spatial analysis.

Figure 15: Group 2 - Pilot cases with high concentration in SELECTED urban OR tourist infrastructure

Figure 16: Group 3 - Pilot cases with little concentration of urban and tourist infrastructure

7 Conclusions and perspectives for the project

Recreation and tourism are part of cultural ecosystems services. Furthermore, the literature also considers most other cultural ecosystems services. Following Maes et al. (2013), we consider also provisioning services as water and food, as they are directly relevant for tourism. We therefore defined eight main categories for ecosystems services for this work: Provision of local freshwater, Provision of local food, Recreation and ecotourism, Aesthetics / beauty, Spiritual / religious meaning, Learning and teaching, Cultural heritage, and Inspiration, Sense of place. The survey conducted amongst tourists and tourist workers identified that most respondents value Freshwater provision, Local food provision and Cultural heritage as the most important ecosystem services (section 4). The examples from the cities shown in section 5 illustrate though the wide variety of ecosystem services provided in different places in the pilot cases. A potential which probably could be focused more on in the light of more sustainable tourism patterns. The quantitative overview of the spatial environment provided in section 6 shows the different character and conditions in the pilot cases. We grouped the cases into

- 1) bigger cities, which experience pressure from urban as well as tourist infrastructure,
- 2) cities which experience pressure from selected urban or touristic infrastructure (e.g. smaller places with high tourism as the cities on Tenerife, or smaller urban areas with however significant transport infrastructure) and
- 3) cities with rural hinterland and a higher share of nature areas.

In all three groups, ecosystem services are under different pressure but, when preserved and maintained as shown by the examples, can also contribute to sustainable and eco-friendly tourism.

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